

1 **A nuclear mechanism for effector function in the attaching/effacing bacteria Enterohemorrhagic E.**
2 **coli (EHEC).**

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7 EHEC belong to a group of pathogens known as attaching/effacing pathogens which use specific cellular
8 attributes to infect cells through mechanisms involving attachment to the host. We measured total
9 transcription in Caco-2 cells following in vitro infection with EHEC or an EHEC mutant deficient in
10 expression of the bacterial effector EspF. The only major difference in gene expression
11 transcriptome-wide in cells infected with wildtype EHEC or an EHEC EspF deletion mutant were
12 expression of the transcription factor Hes1: cells infected with EHEC EspF deletion mutant were mostly
13 defective in Hes1 activation. We present here evidence for a nuclear mechanism for EspF function in an
14 attaching/effacing bacteria.

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